

Batten plates effectiveness on the flexural and lateral – torsional buckling of steel I members

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ABSTRACT

A way of mitigating the negative effects of flexural buckling and lateral torsional buckling (LTB) is the use of batten plates. Batten plates, at appropriate locations along the member are welded to the flanges thus resulting in an increase of flexural and LTB resistance.

The aim of this paper is to investigate their effectiveness and to find their optimum position along the member in regard to the before mentioned buckling phenomena.

First the effectiveness of batten plates on flexural buckling of I columns (pin ended columns) is investigated. A comprehensive study of different configurations and positions of batten plates together with different member sizes is carried out. Batten plates effectiveness is assessed through the elastic critical force of the member (N_{cr}) which is calculated analytically using a novel simplified expression.

In the case of LTB the same approach is followed. Member sizes together with the batten plates configurations and locations are varied and elastic critical lateral torsional buckling moment (M_{cr}) is calculated. Only uniform bending of a simple beam is analysed.

As a result of this study optimum positions of the batten plates in the cases of flexural and LTB are identified. Batten plates, depending on their width and thickness, can increase the N_{cr} from 7 % up to 50%. Their effectiveness is more pronounced in the case of LTB where this increase can be significantly more.

Although an increase in N_{cr} or M_{cr} does not necessarily mean the same increase in member resistance the obtained results indicate that batten plates could be a good and cost effective way of increasing the flexural and LTB resistance of I members.

This paper is meant to be a stepping stone towards further numerical and experimental investigations.

Keywords: flexural buckling, lateral torsional buckling, batten plates, batten plates effectiveness

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel structural members due to inherent high strength of steel as a structural material are usually relatively slender. If these members are subjected to compression (fully or partly) they are susceptible to various forms of buckling. The occurrence of some form of buckling decreases the member resistance, sometimes significantly.

In order to keep buckling under control special measures must be taken. The most common and widespread method is the appropriate use of lateral restraints. Lateral restraints (discrete or continuous) are provided along the member thus lowering its buckling length and consequently increasing its buckling resistance. These lateral restraints are generally some additional steel members with adequate resistance and stiffness. They inevitable lead to a higher overall cost of the building but nevertheless they are a way more economic approach than a simple increases of member cross section size.

In this paper an alternative method for the increase of buckling resistance of I members is explored, namely the use of batten plates. Batten plates of appropriate width and thickness are welded to the flanges of I members thus locally forming a closed cross section as shown in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. I member with batten plates

The hypothesis is that this local reinforcement/stiffening will lead to a measurable increase in buckling resistance, mainly flexural and lateral torsional buckling resistance. Also if the increase in buckling resistance turns out to be significant it is expected that the use of batten plates is a more economic approach than the use of lateral restraints.

In order to test this hypothesis first some questions need answering. First of all there is the question of the optimum location of batten plates along the member. For flexural buckling it may be obvious but for lateral torsional buckling it is not. Secondly, there is the question of the batten plates width and thickness. Does an increase in batten plates width and thickness lead to a proportional increase in buckling resistance of the member? Lastly, is the use of batten plates worthwhile i.e. do they lead to a significant increase in buckling resistance?

The aim of this paper is to investigate and try to answer the before laid out questions. Investigated phenomena are flexural and lateral torsional buckling. The batten plates influence and effectiveness is assessed through elastic critical force in the case of flexural buckling or through elastic critical lateral torsional buckling moment for lateral torsional buckling.

2 BATTEN PLATES AND FLEXURAL BUCKLING

In this section of the paper the influence of batten plates on the flexural buckling resistance of I columns is explored. Hot rolled pin ended columns under constant axial force are investigated. As it was stated before the value for elastic critical buckling force (N_{cr}) is chosen as a measure for batten plates effectiveness.

Keeping this in mind perhaps the most vital step in our analysis is the derivation of an expression (hopefully a closed one) or procedure for the calculation of N_{cr} .

The value of N_{cr} depends on the batten plates configuration mainly their number, location along the member and their stiffness. Taking all these factors into account make the problem of determining the expression for N_{cr} rather complex. In order to simplify the problem some assumptions can be made. Due to flexural buckling very nature and boundary conditions that are investigated in this paper the obvious optimum location for batten plates is the mid-span of the column. The most practical and cost effective solution would be to reinforce the column with one pair of batten plates placed symmetrically about its mid-span as shown in *Fig. 2*.

Similar problem was analysed by Timoshenko in (1). He derived an analytical procedure for determining the N_{cr} in the cases of columns with changes in cross section. This procedure with slight modifications could also be applied to our case. By numerically solving a transcendental equation with regard to the second moment of inertia for the unreinforced and reinforced part of the column the value for N_{cr} can be calculated. Nevertheless the use of this procedure in practice proved to be impractical and time consuming.

I_{z1} is the second moment of inertia of the cross section without the batten plates
 I_{z2} is the second moment of inertia of the cross section with the batten plates
 l is the column length
 b is the batten plates width
 $2a$ is the length of the column without the batten plates

Fig. 2. Analysed batten plates configuration for flexural buckling

Bearing this in mind Subotić in a paper that is currently under review proposed a simplified expression for determining the value of N_{cr} for I columns under constant axial force with one pair of batten plates placed symmetrically around the mid-span of the column. Using Eq. (1) the value for N_{cr} can be easily calculated for various column sizes, batten plates widths and thicknesses.

$$N_{cr,bp} = \frac{\pi^2 E I_{z,eq}}{l^2} \quad (1)$$

where

$N_{cr,bp}$ is the elastic critical buckling force for I columns with one pair of batten plates placed symmetrically around the mid-span of the column,

l is the column length,

$I_{z,eq}$ is the equivalent second moment of inertia.

Equivalent second moment of inertia is determined using Eq. (2).

$$I_{z,eq} = \frac{I_{z2}}{1+4\alpha\beta} \quad (2)$$

With

$$\alpha = \frac{a^2}{l^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = \frac{I_{z2}-I_{z1}}{I_{z1}}$$

The difference between the exact value of $N_{cr,bp}$ calculated using Timoshenko's procedure and the proposed simplified expression is less than 1.15 % and it is always on the safe side thus making it reliable enough for everyday practice and further investigation into batten plates effectiveness.

2.1 Batten plates width influence

In this section of the paper the effectiveness of batten plates with regard to different column sizes and batten plates widths is assessed. Investigated sections are IPE 100, IPE 300, IPE 600, HEA 160, HEA 280, HEA 500, HEB 220, HEB 320 and HEB 550. Batten plates widths are adopted as a portion of the column length. The analysed widths are 0,05 l , 0,075 l , 0,1 l , 0,125 l , 0,15 l , 0,175 and 0,2 l . Batten plates thickness is held constant and adopted as 10 mm. The reference value of the column length is adopted as 8 m.

For the analysed sample (nine section sizes and seven different batten plates widths) the elastic critical buckling force is calculated using Eq. (1). Batten plates effectiveness Δ is calculated as a percentual increase in elastic critical force of the column. Using this approach, together with the manner on how the batten plates widths are chosen, batten plates effectiveness is decoupled from the column length. Obtained results are shown in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 3.

In Fig. 3 a) batten plates effectiveness in the case of IPE sections is shown. It can be seen that batten plates effectiveness is in the range from 8 % to 50 % dependent on the chosen batten plates width. In the case of HEA (Fig. 3 b)) and HEB (Fig. 3 c)) sections the batten plates effectiveness is somewhat lower, ranging from 7 % to 39 % and 6 % to 31 %, respectively.

Obtained results prove that batten plates could be a viable option for mitigating the problem of the flexural buckling.

Table 1. Obtained results

Batten plates width as a portion of the member length		0,05	0,075	0,1	0,125	0,15	0,175	0,2
IPE 100 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	5,66	5,95	6,26	6,59	6,95	7,33	7,75
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	9,97	15,51	21,47	27,88	34,8	42,28	50,36
IPE 300 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	213,532	223,416	233,96	245,21	257,23	270,09	283,86
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	9,2	14,25	19,64	25,40	31,55	38,15	45,16
IPE 600 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	1192,714	1245,02	1300,53	1359,484	1422,13	1488,75	1559,63
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	8,73	13,51	18,57	23,94	29,65	35,73	42,19
HEA 160 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	215,798	224,706	234,11	244,04	254,55	265,64	277,37
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	8,24	12,71	17,43	22,15	27,68	33,25	39,13
HEA 280 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	1656,25	1717,147	1780,87	1847,56	1917,34	1990,33	2066,66
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	7,37	11,32	15,45	19,78	24,3	29,03	33,98
HEA 500 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	3602,13	3732,42	3868,62	4010,98	4159,74	4315,14	4477,44
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	7,26	11,14	15,2	19,43	23,86	28,49	33,24
HEB 220 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	985,24	1019,606	1055,438	1092,79	1131,713	1172,25	1214,465
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	7,01	10,74	14,63	18,69	22,91	27,32	31,91
HEB 320 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	3186,088	3288,642	3395,01	3505,271	3619,516	3737,809	3860,2
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	6,48	9,91	13,46	17,15	20,97	24,92	29,02
HEB 500 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	4531,49	4688,78	4852,74	5023,595	5201,569	5386,883	5579,735
	Effectiveness ratio Δ (%)	6,98	10,69	14,56	18,59	22,80	27,11	31,72

Fig. 3. Batten plates effectiveness for different hot rolled I sections

For a rational batten plates width of 0,1 l an average increase in elastic critical buckling force of 19 % in the case of IPE sections can be regarded as significant.

Batten plates effectiveness for HEA and HEB sections is lower due to smaller relative difference between the second moment of inertia of parts of the column with and without the batten plates. With the increase in this relative difference (parameter β) the batten plates effectiveness increases.

The relationship between batten plates effectiveness and their width is slightly nonlinear. It can be nicely described with a second order polynomial.

Batten plates effectiveness is more pronounced with their larger widths. So in the case of IPE 100 and a batten plates width of 0,2 l their effectiveness is nearly 50 %. Although this value of effectiveness is exceptional some caution is advised. First of all there is the question of economy. Larger batten plates width mean more steel and larger manufacturing cost. Also an increase in elastic critical force doesn't lead to an equal increase in flexural buckling resistance.

2.2 Batten plates thickness influence

In this section of the paper influence of batten plates thickness on their effectiveness is investigated. The same sample of column sections as before is analysed. Batten plates width and column length are held constant. The adopted batten plates width is 0,1 l while the reference value for column length is 8 m. The thickness of batten plates is varied in the range from 4 mm to 14 mm with the increment of 1 mm. Batten plates effectiveness is calculated and plotted against the batten plates thickness for different column sizes. The obtained results are shown in *Table 2* and portrayed in *Fig. 4*.

Table 2. Obtained results

Batten plates thickness (mm)		4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
IPE 100 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	6,099	6,148	6,18	6,211	6,232	6,249	6,263	6,267	6,2835	6,2915	6,298
	Δ (%)	18,3	19,26	19,95	20,48	20,88	21,21	21,47	21,69	21,88	22,03	22,17
IPE 300 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	225,64	228,0	229,763	231,155	232,272	233,19	233,96	234,606	235,16	235,66	236,07
	Δ (%)	15,39	16,59	17,50	18,21	18,79	19,26	19,64	19,98	20,26	20,51	20,73
IPE 600 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	1248,7	1262,8	1273,7	1282,4	1289,6	1295,52	1300,53	1304,81	1308,52	1311,76	1314,6
	Δ (%)	13,84	15,13	16,12	16,92	17,57	18,11	18,57	18,96	19,3	19,59	19,85
HEA 160 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	223,6	226,32	228,504	230,289	231,777	233,035	234,11	235,044	235,859	236,576	237,212
	Δ (%)	12,16	13,52	14,62	15,51	16,26	16,89	17,43	17,90	18,31	18,67	18,99
HEA 280 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	1696,4	1717,1	1734,2	1748,6	1760,9	1771,6	1780,87	1789,1	1796,3	1802,7	1808,6
	Δ (%)	9,98	11,32	12,43	13,36	14,16	14,853	15,45	15,98	16,45	16,87	17,26
HEA 500 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	3684,7	3729,3	3766,5	3797,9	3824,8	3848,2	3868,6	3886,6	3902,6	3916,9	3929,8
	Δ (%)	9,72	11,05	12,15	13,09	13,89	14,59	15,20	15,73	16,21	16,63	17,02
HEB 220 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	1004,1	1016,2	1026,5	1035,3	1042,9	1049,6	1055,4	1060,6	1065,3	1069,5	1073,2
	Δ (%)	9,06	10,38	11,49	12,45	13,27	13,99	14,63	15,2	15,71	16,16	16,57
HEB 320 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	3231,7	3269,1	3301,4	3329,4	3353,9	3375,7	3395,01	3412,3	3427,9	3442,1	3454,9
	Δ (%)	8,01	9,26	10,34	11,28	12,10	12,82	13,46	14,05	14,57	15,04	15,47
HEB 500 l = 8 m	$N_{cr, bp}$ (kN)	4619,8	4675,1	4721,8	4761,7	4796,1	4826,2	4852,74	4876,2	4897,2	4916,1	4993,1
	Δ (%)	9,06	10,37	11,47	12,41	13,23	13,94	14,56	15,12	15,61	16,06	16,46

As it can be seen in *Fig. 4 a), b) and c)* the effectiveness of batten plates while varying their thickness changes only slightly. The increase in batten plates thickness of 250 % results in a merely 7,5 % increase in their effectiveness. This clearly indicates that the batten plates thickness can be disregarded as a significant influential factor. It is interesting to point out that the influence of the

thickness of batten plates is more pronounced in the case of HEA and HEB sections than in the case of IPE sections.

Fig. 4. Batten plates effectiveness for their different thickness

The relationship between batten plates thickness and their effectiveness is nonlinear with signs of a asymptotic behaviour.

In practice the thickness of the batten plates should be chosen with regard to the overall weight of the column and the possibility of local buckling. In the authors opinion the thickness of the batten plates should be chosen so that the possibility of local buckling is prevented (preferably class 1 or 2 cross section).

3 BATTEN PLATES AND LATERAL TORSIONAL BUCKLING

Lateral torsional buckling is a complex spatial instability phenomenon. Lateral displacement of the compressed part is accompanied by the twisting and warping of the cross section. Due to their relatively low torsional stiffness I beams are particularly prone to this type of buckling. Lateral torsional buckling can significantly reduce the resistance of I beams thus making it a problem that needs to be dealt with.

One possible and novel way of doing so is the use of batten plates. By welding the batten plates to the beam flanges a set of local closed cross section segments are formed with very large torsional stiffness.

The assumption is that these local closed cross section segments will result in a significant increase in lateral torsional buckling resistance of the member. Bearing in mind the very nature of lateral torsional buckling resistance batten plates are expected to be more efficient than in the case of flexural buckling.

But like in the case of flexural buckling in order to start utilizing the beneficiary effect of batten plates some questions needs to be answered. There is the question of the optimum position of the batten plates along the beam as well as the influence of batten plates width and thickness on their effectiveness. Answering these questions is a path filled with obstacles and it is considerable more complex than in the case of flexural buckling.

The first obstacle is the problem of elastic critical lateral torsional buckling moment (M_{cr}) for I beams with batten plates which is perhaps the most important tool for initial evaluation of batten plates effectiveness.

Not many researchers tried to tackle this problem and those who did (2, 3 and 4) had limited success. Closed form expression or practical and reliable numerical procedure for determining M_{cr} for I beams with batten plates hasn't been derived yet. Taking this into consideration the same kind of analysis as was carried out for flexural buckling is not possible.

So when it comes to lateral torsional buckling and batten plates the question that will be discussed in this paper is the optimum position of the batten plates along the beam. Some assumptions are made in order to simplify this problem. Only the case where there are two pairs of batten plates symmetrically positioned around the middle of the beam is analysed (*Fig. 5*). It is also assumed that there is no warping in the closed cross sections segments.

Fig. 5. Batten plates configuration for lateral torsional buckling

In order to find the optimum position of the batten plates M_{cr} is calculated using an analytical procedure.

The beam is considered as a sum of open and closed cross section segments as shown in *Fig. (5)*. Appropriate stability differential equations are set for those segments.

For open cross section segments differential equations in the form of *Eq. (3)* are used.

$$EI_w \frac{\partial^4 \varphi(x)}{\partial x^4} - GI_t \frac{\partial^2 \varphi(x)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{M_y^2}{EI_z} \varphi(x) = 0 \quad (3)$$

General solution of *Eq. (3)* can be written in the following manner.

$$\varphi(x) = C_1 \sin mx + C_2 \cos mx + C_3 \sinh nx + C_4 \cosh nx \quad (4)$$

with

$$m = \sqrt{-c + \sqrt{c^2 + d}} \quad n = \sqrt{c + \sqrt{c^2 + d}} \quad c = \frac{GI_t}{2EI_w} \quad \text{and} \quad d = \frac{M_y^2}{EI_w EI_z}$$

Differential equations used for closed cross section segments for which is assumed that there is no warping are in the form of *Eq. (5)*.

$$GI_t \frac{\partial^2 \varphi(x)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{M_y^2}{EI_z} \varphi(x) = 0 \quad (5)$$

For *Eq. (5)* the general solution is as follows.

$$\varphi(x)_2 = C_5 \sin px + C_6 \cos px \quad (6)$$

with

$$p^2 = \frac{M_y^2}{GI_{t2} EI_{z2}}$$

By using the appropriate boundary conditions at the ends of the beam and between segments a system of homogenous linear equations is obtained. In order for this system to have a non-trivial solution the determinant of the system must be zero. Using this condition the values for M_{cr} can be calculated.

To further simplify the analysed problem showed in *Fig. (5)* the symmetry property is used. In this manner only three segments together with the following boundary conditions needs to be analysed.

$$\begin{array}{lll} \text{At } x = 0 & \text{At } x = x_1 \text{ and } x = x_2 & \text{At } x = l/2 \\ \varphi_1 = 0 & \varphi_L = \varphi_R & \frac{d\varphi_3}{dx} = 0 \end{array} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d^2\varphi_1}{dx^2} = 0$$

$$u_L = u_R$$

$$GI_{t1} \frac{d\varphi_3}{dx} - EI_{w1} \frac{d^3\varphi_3}{dx^3} = 0$$

$$M_{TL} = M_{TR}$$

The value for M_{cr} is obtained from the determinant of this ten by ten system of equations using a numerical procedure created in Microsoft Excel.

Since the appropriate procedure for the calculation of the M_{cr} has been defined the optimum position of the batten plates along the I beam can be now explored.

Three different beam sizes are considered namely IPE 300, HEA 280 and HEB 550. The length of the beams is 8 m and they are subjected to uniform bending. The starting point of batten plates (distance a) is varied along the beam from the beam ends to the mid-span with the increment of 0,05 times l . Batten plates thickness is adopted as 10 mm. The width of one batten plate is 0,05 l .

Using the above defined procedure the values for M_{cr} are calculated. Obtained results are shown in the following figure.

Fig. 6. Batten plates effectiveness with regard to their different position along the member

The results in Fig. (6) clearly indicate that the optimum position of the two pairs of batten plates for I beams subjected to uniform bending is near the ends of the member at about 0,1 times the beam length measured from beam ends. Similar findings are reported in (2), (3), (4). When batten plates are positioned near the mid-span of the beam they are practically ineffective.

Batten plates effectiveness in the case of lateral torsional buckling is clearly larger than in the case of flexural buckling. As opposite to the case of flexural buckling in the case of lateral torsional buckling batten plates are more effective for HEA and HEB sections than for IPE sections. This is expected because of the very shape of HEA and HEB sections.

An increase of 125 % in M_{cr} for IPE 300 is rather large and should be treated with some reservation. Although in (2), the only paper that approached this problem analytically, similar percentages are reported they could not be confirmed in numerical eigen buckling analysis carried out in Ansys software in (3) and (4). A comprehensive comparative analysis is difficult to carry out because of the lack of data and the fact that different authors analysed different cases (different section sizes, member and batten plates length etc.).

Regardless of the actual effectiveness ratio of the batten plates relationship between the value for M_{cr} and the position of the batten plates shown in Fig. (6) is reported also in (2, 3 and 4).

If the increase in M_{cr} is only 30 percent as reported in (3) and (4) this is still a significant increase and thus indicate that the use of batten plates is a viable option for increasing the lateral torsional buckling resistance of I beams. Further investigations in this field are sorely needed.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper an alternative method for increasing the flexural and lateral torsional buckling resistance of I members is explored, namely the use of batten plates. Member sizes together with batten plates position along the member, width and thickness were varied and elastic critical buckling force or moment was obtained. Batten plates effectiveness Δ is calculated as a percentual increase in elastic critical force/moment of the column/beam.

In the case of flexural buckling the influence of column size, batten plates width and thickness on their effectiveness was explored. Nine different hot rolled I sections together with seven different batten plates widths and eleven different batten plates thickness were analysed.

The obtained results show that batten plates are most effective for IPE sections. For a rational batten plates width of 0,1 times the column length the average increase in elastic critical buckling force for IPE sections is nearly 20 % (19,88 % to be precise). With larger batten plates widths their effectiveness increases reaching even 50 % (IPE 100 section and a batten plate width of 0,2 l). For HEA and HEB sections batten plates effectiveness is somewhat lower ranging from 13 % to 18 %. This is due to smaller relative difference between the second moment of inertia of parts of the column with and without the batten plates.

Batten plates thickness can be disregarded as a significant influential factor for their effectiveness. With the increase in batten plates thickness of 250 % the maximum calculated increase in batten plates effectiveness is only 7,5 %.

In the case of lateral torsional buckling two pairs of batten plates symmetrically positioned around the middle of the beam were analysed. Beam sizes together with the starting point of batten plates along the beam were varied and elastic critical lateral torsional buckling moment was calculated using an analytical procedure. Obtained results clearly show that for the analysed configuration of batten plates their optimum starting position is 0,1 times the beam length measured from the beam ends. On the other hand the calculated average batten plates effectiveness of 155 % should be treated with some reservation. Although in (2), the only paper that approached this problem analytically, similar percentages are reported they could not be confirmed in numerical eigen buckling analysis carried out in Ansys software in (3) and (4). One possible explanation for this could be that the assumption of no warping in closed section segments is an oversimplification that results in an unrealistically high values for M_{cr} . As was stated before further analytical and numerical research is need into this topic.

All in all obtained results indicate that the use of batten plates could be a viable measure for increasing flexural and lateral torsional buckling resistance of I members. Beneficiary effect of batten plates is more pronounced in the case of lateral torsional buckling where it can even challenge the use of lateral restraints.

It is important to point out that an increase in elastic critical buckling force/moment of the member doesn't necessary lead to an equal increase in its flexural or lateral torsional buckling resistance. Bearing this in mind a significant amount of research still needs to be done in order to start utilizing the beneficiary effect of batten plates in everyday practice. This paper is envisioned as a first stepping stone towards that goal.

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